

AUTOMATIC RENDERING OF RAMATI’S LUDUS MUSICALIS SCORES

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ABSTRACT

Ludus musicalis – Zwölf Modelle für Schulorchester (12 Models for School Orchestras) is a collection of compositions by Roman Haubenstock-Ramati that adopts “non-conventional” ways to encode the musical score. Sets of rules are provided and used by interpreters to decode various parameters. In this sense the compositions contain aleatoric elements that might vary between performances. We developed a Python tool that allows for processing an image of a score in the format of *Ludus musicalis* (1-2 in particular) and generates a MIDI rendering as well as a MusicXML transcription. With this tool we want to provide users with a way to familiarize themselves with this type of notation, allowing them to quickly generate possible renditions of these complex materials. Users can also draw new scores following *Ludus musicalis* rules which can be performed for live audiences, thus allowing a general public to interact with a form of notation not widely known.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of contemporary music practices different systems for notations have been employed and developed. These non-conventional notations are often defined in reference to the so-called Common Western Notation (CWN).

Focusing our scope on the 20th century, changes were introduced as a consequence of new composition and performance techniques, aesthetic considerations, and issues arising from the availability of new instruments (e.g. electronics, magnetic tape) with new expressive capabilities. These issues fall outside of the scope of this contribution, but a large body of work exists, see for example [1].

In the '50s and '60s, for example, the composers of the New York School (including John Cage, Morton Feldman, Earle Brown, and Christian Wolff) began experimenting with indeterminacy and investigated graphic notation as a way to restrict and reinvent the information provided to performers [2].

The topics of form and notation are central to the work of composer and publisher Roman Haubenstock-Ramati who in 1970 published *Ludus musicalis – Zwölf Modelle für Schulorchester* (12 Models for School Orchestras). Ramati discusses his ideas on the topic of notation in [3].

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In preparation of a concert dedicated to music with non-linear and aleatoric elements we identified *Ludus musicalis* as an extremely interesting case. Its graphical notation provokes aleatoric interpretation while retaining compositional structure. The form of the score even affects the seating arrangement of the ensemble. Its reading rules allow the score to be performed by ensembles with any instrumentation.

The present contribution is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the composition *Ludus musicalis*, its notation, and the sets of rules used for interpretation and performance. Section 3 discusses the implementation of a Python tool capable of reading and performing such scores.

While not explicitly concerned with the task of providing a transcription in CWN, this work is inspired by [4]. We share some common approaches and goals such as the rediscovery of a repertoire, the comprehension of a notation system, and the possibility of interaction for a general public.

2. LUDUS MUSICALIS

Roman Haubenstock-Ramati’s *Ludus musicalis* was published in 1970 by Universal Edition (Vienna, Austria) where he also worked as editor and music consultant.

In the introduction Ramati refers to “musical graphics”, an expression which he used for the first time in the exhibition catalogue in Donaueschingen in 1959 [5]. It was used to describe a new type of notation for musical works and referred to both scores and solo voices.

Since then, the term has been used for different forms of notation, including “mise en page” (a temporal and spatial division of what is normally notated) (see e.g. [6, 7], these references are in German), “action” and “association notations”, where elements outside the standard notation are used, and which might lead to a “form” of improvisation.

In this sense the use of elements extraneous to the usual notation can serve various purposes such as the introduction of variability (in the words of the author “the possibility [for the performer] of changing”) to details (microstructure) as well as to the form (macrostructure), thus encouraging a “greater freedom and spontaneity in playing.”

For Ramati the creative engagement with the problems of notation can lead to the emergence of new forms of music.

The 12 compositions are (translations by the authors):

1. PUNKTE (Dots)
2. PIZZICATI
3. GLISSANDI

4. KONTINUITÄT (Continuity)
5. MELODISCHE FLOSKELN (Melodic phrases)
6. DIE KLEINEN SCHRITTE (Small steps)
7. KONSTELLATIONEN (Constellations)
8. GERÄUSCHE (Noises)
9. STUFEN (Steps)
10. FLÄCHEN (Planes)
11. STATISCHE RHYTHMEN (Static rhythms)
12. DYNAMISCHE TONREPETITIONEN (Dynamic tone repetitions).

Each composition is presented both in its original form and in its “crab shape” (mirrored on the vertical axis). For each composition a set of rules is provided in order to interpret the notation. Some symbols and rules are used in multiple compositions, alone or combined with others.

In these compositions material is organized on the page inside a square allowing each of these forms to be presented four times by rotating the page. This creates different forms and possibilities for executing the musical sequence, such as performing the different positions (orientations) one after the other, or organizing orchestral groups around the score to perform some of the positions simultaneously.

The horizontal axis represents the time domain. The individual sound phenomena are realized proportionally (true to scale). This representation corresponds to the principle of “proportional meters”, which is what Ramati calls his adaptation of the space-time notation that has been in use since the early 1950s. Each piece should last between one and three minutes.

The vertical axis represents the pitch domain. Like the horizontal axis, it is interpreted using the same “proportional meters”. The range should normally correspond to the full pitch range of the instrument, however the conductor can assign specific registers to players or groups.

In this collection of scores different symbols and metaphors are used. Some symbols are discrete and placed separately from each other, while in other occasions continuous elements (e.g. curves) are overlapped with each other. In case of continuous elements a question that arises for our work is what parameters would be relevant to extract in order to perform a rendering.

For these reasons our current approach addresses discrete symbols, and we will be focusing on **Punkte** and **Pizzicati**, so we will introduce these two sets of rules as presented by Ramati in the accompanying material.

2.1 Punkte

The piece contains only short sounds, namely ○ ● as single sounds, ⊗ ● as double sounds (♩♯) or ⊗ ● as triple sounds (♩♯♯).

The types and sizes of the note heads have special meanings for the individual instrument groups and are presented in Table 1.

Strings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● arco ordinario ○ arco sul ponticello 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>pp</i> ○ <i>mp</i> ● <i>f</i> ○ <i>ff</i>
Wind	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● woodwinds ○ brass 	Dynamics as strings
Keyboards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Single note ● 2 adjacent notes ● 3 adjacent notes ● 4 adjacent notes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>pp</i> ● <i>f/ff</i>
Percussions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ soft mallets ● hard mallets ○ membranophone ● idiophone 	Dynamics as strings

Table 1. Rules for Punkte.

2.2 Pizzicati

One of the original scores of Pizzicati is presented in Figure 1, courtesy of the editor.

Figure 1. The score of Pizzicati. (© Copyright 1970 by Universal Edition A.G., Wien / UE20015)

The goal is to achieve high density, continuity and homogeneity of the timbre. Only one symbol is adopted in the score: ⊕.

Players can play in different registers, with larger or smaller ranges (but not smaller than two octaves).

The four small structures (of the 5 clusters that can be identified in the score) could be realized with the wind instruments in a noisy way (clattering, with a lot of air and little sound).

The strings play pizzicato (plucked) or “col legno battuto” (with the wood [being hit]). The pizzicato can be played normally, à la Bartók (very sharp, with the string snapping on the fingerboard), with nails and with glissando (up or down).

Piano is played inside the instrument. The strings are made to resonate in the appropriate register with the help of fingers, palms, brushes, brooms, plectrums, etc.

3. THE APPLICATION

For the concert performance of *Ludus musicalis* we planned to involve both human musicians and machine performance. The audience is asked to select a score which is then preprocessed by the machine. It is then able to perform any of the reading directions autonomously while others are played by human musicians.

We employed Python, a modern versatile programming language known for its simplicity and readability. We structured our work as a Jupyter Notebook allowing for interactive computing, and presenting the user with the source code as well as auxiliary information.

Python’s standard library and extensive ecosystem of third-party packages allowed us to tackle diverse tasks with relative ease delegating to already existing packages’ specific functionalities (e.g. template matching, image processing etc.).

The project is available on GitHub.¹ For copyright reasons it is not possible to distribute the original scores, we therefore include as examples two scores created by a user “in the style” of *Ludus musicalis* Punkte and Pizzicati.

The workflow of the system is as follows:

1. Select input image (or acquire from a webcam)
2. Set the bounding box for the score
3. Select the rule-set (Punkte or Pizzicati) and the templates used for matching
4. Multi Template Matching
5. MIDI and MusicXML Rendering

3.1 Multi Template Matching

The implementation comes from the package MTM² presented in [8].

Template matching algorithms are used to find the location of relevant objects in 2D-images. This particular approach does not require data pre-processing, or annotated data for training.

In our case, depending on the score we are processing, we have only one (Pizzicati) or six templates (Punkte).

To improve the recognition performance we generate an augmented template list. This is needed as we can potentially present the score in any orientation, and when using a different image we can have a different scaling factor (e.g. the distance of the image from the lens).

¹ <https://github.com/Murivan/LudusMusicalis>, last access Feb. 2025.

² <https://github.com/multi-template-matching/MultiTemplateMatching-Python>, last access: Feb. 2025.

Figure 2. Example of the results of the template matching phase. Rightmost section of Pizzicati. (© Copyright 1970 by Universal Edition A.G., Wien / UE20015)

This means that on top of the original templates we produce scaled versions between 50% and 150%, 90° rotations, and mirroring on X axis, Y axis, and both. For every template in the original list we build 176 templates in total.

While this contributes to slowing down the process, testing it with a high resolution image of 2500×2500 pixels, and templates of around 30×30 pixels resulted in ~ 10 seconds for Pizzicati (176 templates) and ~ 60 seconds for Punkte (1056 templates) on laptop computers equipped with 16 GB of RAM and Apple Silicon M1 or Intel 13th Gen CPUs. Using the `memory_profile` utility we can estimate a memory consumption between 1 and 2 GB for the entire application.

The following parameters can be configured for the template matching algorithms:

- Score Type: Normalised Square Difference (NSD), Normalised Cross-Correlation (NCC), 0-mean Normalized Cross-Correlation (0-mean NCC)
- Expected number of objects N (if known)
- Score Threshold (Range 0-1)
- Maximal overlap (Range 0-1): value allowed for the ratio of the Intersection Over Union (IoU) area between overlapping bounding boxes.

Figure 2 shows the rightmost block of Pizzicati. Highlighted in red are the recognized templates. It can be seen that some elements have not been recognized, e.g. two symbols whose bounding boxes are substantially overlapped, highlighted in green.

3.2 MIDI and MusicXML Rendering

The output of the template matching phase is a list of bounding boxes (X, Y, Height, Width) with labels attached.

Our first task is to create four lists sorting our labels based on their position for the four different possible reading directions (left to right, right to left, top to bottom, bottom to top). Once we have the four lists we rescale their coordinates between 0 and 1 for the “horizontal” (of that particular list) axis (Time), and between 0 and 127 (MIDI Pitch) for the “vertical” axis. From this point the lists can be processed in a similar manner.

The application contains a data structure mapping some common musical instruments’ names, their corresponding GM Program Numbers, Range (used to appropriately scale the vertical axis), and their family (to employ the correct set of rules for performance).

The user has control over the following parameters:

- Tempo (in BPM)
- Total length of the performance (in seconds)
- Individual note duration (e.g. sixteenth, thirty-second)
- Instruments performing the individual parts

For the MIDI conversion the number of ticks per beat (conventionally per quarter note, here set by default at 480) and the number of microseconds per tick are computed. At this stage the sorted lists can be seen as containing “events” (such as one or more NoteOn MIDI messages) that have to be interpreted according to one of the sets of rules.

One situation we need to address is that whenever we generate a NoteOn we need to generate a corresponding NoteOff sometime in the future. MIDI files encode the timing of events as a delta time from the previous event.

The solution is to use the original data structure, and add new events (e.g. NoteOff) with their “absolute” timing, sort it based on the timing attribute, and finally convert to delta timing by subtracting from the timing of the current event the timing of the previous event.

In Punkte, symbols can generate sequences of 1 to 3 notes (for all instruments), they can also generate chords for keyboards. Dynamics can also be altered.

Currently the rules for keyboards and wind instruments are fully implemented. For strings, dynamics are implemented but no distinctions are made between \bullet (arco ordinario/sul ponticello). For percussions, Indefinite Pitch is implemented sending messages on MIDI channel 10, while for Definite Pitch no distinction is currently made between soft and hard mallets.

For Pizzicati, considering that our output is a MIDI rendering, we do not have a way to express for example that the piano should be played from the inside, with brushes or plectrums. While this information is not encoded in the MIDI file, the file can still be used in a prepared piano. Similarly for strings, as the indication of “how” the pizzicati has to be played cannot be encoded with MIDI, the choice is to pass the GM Program Number 46 (Pizzicato Strings). This information can later be used to determine

Figure 3. Piano roll of a MIDI Rendering of *Ludus musicalis* 4 performed from left to right (orientation of the page in the original edition).

which synthesizer, or sample library, has to be adopted in the performance.

MIDI renderings and MusicXML “transcriptions” are provided for the individual tracks, as well as a “full” version containing all four.

An example of MIDI rendering is presented in Figure 3. It can be noted how the “shape” of the score is visible in the piano roll.

MusicXML files are generated using the music21 package [9] starting from the MIDI performance and applying a quantization step. This is a parameter that determines the minimum length of a note/rest, and the default value is thirty-second. We present an example in Figure 4. This is the same area depicted in Figure 2.

4. DISCUSSION

It is important to note that in our work we focused on a literal interpretation of the image, according to the rules, rather than the type of interpretation of a human performer. Quite likely a performer will not be able to focus on all the symbols that are depicted in the score (e.g. in Punkte there are more than 200 symbols, and considerably more in Pizzicati), nor to follow exactly the proportional meters for time and pitch. Similarly even the “density” of the events would prevent a performer from being able to execute them all. Our goal was to provide a way to look into these materials and present them to non-expert listeners.

At the current stage 2 of the 12 rule sets are implemented, and in particular we focused on the ones adopting “discrete symbols” rather than continuous ones (e.g. Die Kleinen

Figure 4. Transcription with music21 of the initial part of Pizzicati 3, performed in the direction from right to left.

Schritte). They pose challenges in terms of machine-vision algorithms and what parameters should be extracted by the analysis stage.

There are also a number of challenges to consider when making the system “stage ready” for a live performance that involves scanning scores in real-time. In particular the stability and reliability of the system are paramount, followed by the computational resources allocated for the entire process. If we are working with a score that has to be acquired with a camera, situations such as optical distortion (e.g. presenting the surface of the paper curved), illumination, and orientation of the score are all compounding problems that need to be addressed. Presently the best solution is to use a document-camera (i.e. a camera mounted on a control arm that can be adjusted), providing a flat surface to present the document, and a source of illumination.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

In this contribution we presented an application for the automatic performance of Ramati’s *Ludus musicalis* 1-2. While a more extended experimentation phase has not been performed yet, we believe that performers, scholars, and the general public can all find relevant use cases. This tool can help performers and scholars in understanding possible performances and support them during their studies. The general public can experiment with aleatoric music generating audio (via MIDI) feedback and thus familiarize themselves with the aesthetics of this style. Users can also “extend” the original corpus of *Ludus musicalis* by drawing new scores. The project can be expanded to include more forms from the original composition (e.g. Glissandi), and to allow a mixture of rules to be used in the same composition, similarly to what happens in *Kontinuität* or *Konstellationen*.

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³ <https://kreativ.institute>